

Tool 15

Initial motivations

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 2 – develop) and will help you to consider potential motivations of citizens to initiate participation in your activities.

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer. If you have any further questions about this template, please contact citizenscience@vub.be.

A citizen science project might resonate with participants in different ways and for different reasons. There have been numerous studies on citizen scientists’ motivations. A recent review by Robinson, Kocman, Speyer, and Gerasopoulos (2021)¹ found six main motivations. Use the form below to consider how your project might tap into the following motivations of your (future) citizen scientists:

¹ Robinson, J. A., Kocman, D., Speyer, O., & Gerasopoulos, E. (2021). Meeting volunteer expectations—a review of volunteer motivations in citizen science and best practices for their retention through implementation of functional features in CS tools. *Journal of environmental planning and management*, 64(12), 2089-2113.

Motive	Description	What does the project offer participants with regard to this motive?
Values	The wish to contribute to science or society (i.e. civic responsibility) while helping the environment	
Personal development	Learning opportunities (about the scientific subject area and data collecting and analyzing techniques, environmental awareness, familiar places)	
Carrier and recognition	To gain relevant experience related to their career interests and to gain recognition and other personal benefits for their input	
Social	Social interaction and being part of a community of like-minded individuals	
Recreation	To have fun and to undertake new activities as part of existing recreational activities while commonly being outdoors	